

Non-ideal non-abelian gauge theories

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In this work we introduce some field-theoretic approach for non-abelian gauge theories that takes into account non-ideal effects, in the same lines to the recently proposed and designed for describing non-ideal systems undergoing continuous phase transitions in low-energies. As an example, we study some elementary process at both at three-level as well up to one-loop order. We show that some similar but non-renormalizable theories defined early in literature are not capable of describing such an elementary process up to one-loop order and are limited to furnish results to that process just at three-level. This fact characterizes such theories, at most, as effective ones. The systems approached in the present work displays a relationship between non-ideal properties and fluctuations.

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I. INTRODUCTION

At present, it is well established that q -deformation is linked to the cosmological constant. In particular, this type of deformation can lead to the emergence of a cosmological constant term in three-dimensional quantum gravity [1], as well as in other frameworks within gravitational theory [2–5]. Furthermore, investigations into q -deformation have extended far beyond gravity itself, drawing considerable interest in a wide range of physics disciplines over the past years [6–24].

Motivated by the recently introduced generalized non-ideal a -statistics of Ref. [25], where the Boltzmann-Gibbs exponential distribution is deformed, in this work we propose some field-theoretic tool for studying non-ideal non-abelian gauge theories. In fact, the theory designed for describing the scaling critical behavior of non-ideal low-energy systems undergoing continuous phase transitions [25] has attained satisfactory agreement between theoretical predictions and experimental measured values for the corresponding critical exponents [25]. Such non-ideal systems for which $a \neq 1$, present defects, impurities and inhomogeneities as opposed to ideal ones which are perfect, pure and homogeneous where $a = 1$.

The theory for describing non-ideal systems was called non-ideal statistical field theory (NISFT). It furnished results for the critical exponents up to next-to-leading order (NLO) while similar but non-renormalizable theories were limited to provide results for the same exponents only at LO, thus characterizing them all as effective theories. When a theory is limited to provide physical quantities only up to LO, it is said to be not fundamental and is, at most, effective. On the other hand, when we compute physical quantities up to some desired order beyond the leading one, this theory is fundamental. Equivalently, going to more and more orders in the number of loops, we are describing a given physical phenomenon at all length of scales [26] or loop orders. Just with a renormalizable theory we can compute physical quantities up to more and more loop orders.

Examples of non-renormalizable effective theories include the Schrödinger equation, Fermi's theory of the weak force, chiral perturbation theory, and general relativity. In contrast, the consistent, renormalizable—or fundamental—theories correspond to the four known interactions described by the Standard Model of elementary particles: the electromagnetic, weak, strong, and gravitational forces. The aforementioned effective theories produced results that were generally restricted to the one-loop order. However, while the fundamental renormalizable theories were not yet fully developed, the corresponding non-renormalizable effective theories were still used in calculations, even though their predictions were valid only within limited length scales or at the one-loop level. Although some results, such as those from Fermi theory, matched the correct numerical order of magnitude, they were conceptually incomplete. In fact, they represented only the one-loop contribution, whereas the full effects arise from a sum over multiple contributions—one-, two-, three-loop orders, and beyond. Once the fundamental theories, which include both low- and high-order loop contributions, were established, the inconsistent non-renormalizable effective theories were no longer considered fundamental; at most, they were treated as effective approximations. Consequently, today the fundamental theories describing elementary particles and their interactions are the electromagnetic, weak, and strong forces, which together constitute the Standard Model. In this work, we demonstrate that the proposed theory is capable of describing non-ideal quantum electromagnetic phenomena up to next-to-leading order (NLO), unlike some recently proposed non-renormalizable or effective theories in the literature, which provide results limited to leading order (LO) only.

II. S_a -MATRIX

The ideal Lagrangian density of non-abelian gauge theories in Feynman gauge [27]

$$\mathcal{L} = -\frac{1}{4}(F_{\mu\nu}^a)^2 + \bar{\psi}(i\not{D} - m)\psi - \bar{c}^a \partial^\mu D_\mu^{ac} c^c. \quad (1)$$

can be written by expliciting its interaction terms as

$$\mathcal{L} = \mathcal{L}_0 + \mathcal{L}_{int}, \quad (2)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_0 = -\frac{1}{4}(\partial_\mu A_\nu^a - \partial_\nu A_\mu^a)^2 + \bar{\psi}(i\not{\partial} - m)\psi - \bar{c}^a \partial^2 c^a, \quad (3)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}_{int} = & g A_\mu^a \bar{\psi} \gamma^\mu t^a \psi - g f^{abc} (\partial_\mu A_\nu^a) A^{b\mu} A^{c\nu} \\ & - \frac{1}{4} g^2 (f^{eab} A_\mu^a A_\nu^b) (f^{ecd} A^{c\mu} A^{d\nu}) - g \bar{c}^a f^{abc} \partial^\mu A_\mu^b c^c, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
& -ig^2 [f^{abc} f^{cde} (g^{\mu\rho} g^{\nu\sigma} - g^{\mu\sigma} g^{\nu\rho}) \\
& + f^{ace} f^{bde} (g^{\mu\nu} g^{\rho\sigma} - g^{\mu\sigma} g^{\nu\rho}) \\
& + f^{ade} f^{bce} (g^{\mu\nu} g^{\rho\sigma} - g^{\mu\rho} g^{\nu\sigma})] =
\end{aligned}$$

(13)

Now we display some non-abelian elementary process at LO.

A. $e^+e^- \rightarrow \text{hadrons}$

We can study the $e^+e^- \rightarrow \text{hadrons}$ process at LO by considering the following Feynman diagram [28]

(14)

whose total cross section is given by

$$\sigma_{\text{LO}, a} = R_{\text{had}}^{\gamma 0} \sigma_{0, a}, \quad (15)$$

$$R_{\text{had}}^{\gamma 0} = \sum_{\text{colors}} \sum_{q=u}^b Q_q^2, \quad (16)$$

$$\sigma_{0, a} = \frac{4\pi a^2 \alpha_s^2}{3E_{\text{CM}}^2}, \quad (17)$$

$$\alpha_s = \frac{g^2}{4\pi}. \quad (18)$$

IV. NLO APPROXIMATION

A. $e^+e^- \rightarrow \text{hadrons}$

When we consider the process of e^+e^- annihilation into hadrons [28] up to NLO, we must take into account both LO

(19)

and NLO diagrams

(20)

and

(21)

in the following Eq. [28]

(22)

that furnishes the result

$$\sigma_{\text{NLO}, a}(e^+e^- \rightarrow \text{hadrons}) = R_{\text{had}}^{\gamma^0} \sigma_{0, a} \left(1 + \frac{3a^2 \alpha_s}{4\pi} C_2(r) + \mathcal{O}(\alpha_s^2) \right), \quad (23)$$

which is the non-ideal total cross section for the process aforementioned up to NLO. For $SU(N)$ gauge theories described by a fundamental representation with n_f fermions [27],

$$C(N) = \frac{1}{2}, \quad (24)$$

$$C_2(N) = \frac{N^2 - 1}{2N}, \quad (25)$$

$$C_2(G) = N, \quad (26)$$

where $C(r)$ is a constant defined from $\text{tr}[t_r^a t_r^b] = C(r) \delta^{ab}$ and $C_2(r)$ is the quadratic Casimir operator, both for each representation of the $SU(N)$ group. The constant $C_2(G)$ is the quadratic Casimir operator in the corresponding adjoint representation. Such a cancellation cannot occur in the case of the previously introduced non-renormalizable theories, which are unable to provide this NLO result. Their range is limited to tree-level contributions, as illustrated for certain effective models in Table IV A, thereby identifying them, at most, as effective theories.

B. Renormalization group

We can compute the nonideal radiative correction to the unperturbed photon propagator [36]

(27)

Total cross sections for some non-renormalizable theories
at LO.

$$[29] \sigma_{\text{LO}, \delta_{KLS}} = \frac{4\pi(1 - 2\delta_{KLS})^2 \alpha_s^2}{3E_{\text{CM}}^2}$$

$$[30] \sigma_{\text{LO}, \gamma_{KLS}} = \frac{4\pi(1 - 2\gamma_{KLS})^2 \alpha_s^2}{3E_{\text{CM}}^2}$$

$$[31] \sigma_{\text{LO}, \kappa} = \frac{4\pi\alpha_s^2}{3E_{\text{CM}}^2}$$

$$[32] \sigma_{\text{LO}, q} = \frac{4\pi q^2 \alpha_s^2}{3E_{\text{CM}}^2}$$

$$[33] \sigma_{\text{LO}, q} = \frac{4\pi(3q - 2)^2 \alpha_s^2}{3E_{\text{CM}}^2}$$

$$[34] \sigma_{\text{LO}, q_1, q_2} = \frac{4\pi(q_1^2 + q_2^2)^2 \alpha_s^2}{12E_{\text{CM}}^2}$$

$$[35] \sigma_{\text{LO}, q} = \frac{4\pi(1 + q)^2 \alpha_s^2}{12E_{\text{CM}}^2}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
iD'_{\mu\nu, a}(p) = & \text{---} + \text{---} \text{---} + \\
& \text{---} \text{---} + \text{---} \text{---} \\
& + \text{---} \text{---} , \tag{28}
\end{aligned}$$

$$iS'_{F, a}(p) = \text{---} + \text{---} . \tag{29}$$

The corresponding nonideal Callan-Symanzik equation is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
& \left[M \frac{\partial}{\partial M} + \beta_a(g) \frac{\partial}{\partial g} + n\gamma_{A, a}(g) + m\gamma_{\psi, a}(g) \right] \times \\
& G_a^{(n, m)}(\{x_i\}; M, g) = 0, \tag{30}
\end{aligned}$$

where $G_a^{(n, m)}(\{x_i\}; M, g)$ is the Green's function and M some scale parameter [27]. The functions $\gamma_{A, a}$ and $\gamma_{\psi, a}$ are the rescaling functions of the gauge boson and fermion fields, respectively. Then we obtain [27]

$$\beta_a(g) = -\frac{a^2 g^3}{16\pi^2} \left(\frac{11}{3} C_2(G) - \frac{4}{3} n_f C(r) \right), \tag{31}$$

$$\gamma_{A, a}(g) = -\frac{a^2 g^2}{16\pi^2} \left(\frac{5}{3} C_2(G) - \frac{4}{3} n_f C(r) \right), \tag{32}$$

$$\gamma_{\psi, a}(g) = \frac{a^2 g^2}{16\pi^2} C_2(r), \tag{33}$$

C. Running coupling constant

For $SU(N)$ gauge theories, see Eqs. (24)-(26), described by a fundamental representation with n_f fermions [27], the $\beta_a(g)$ -function assumes the form

$$\beta_a(g) = -\frac{a^2 g^3}{16\pi^2} \left(\frac{11}{3}N - \frac{2}{3}n_f \right). \quad (34)$$

Thus the running coupling constant of the theory approaches zero as momenta approach large values as

$$g^2(k) = \frac{g^2}{1 + \frac{a^2 g^2}{16\pi^2} \left(\frac{11}{3}N - \frac{2}{3}n_f \right) \log \left(\frac{k^2}{M^2} \right)}. \quad (35)$$

V. NON-IDEAL QUANTUM CHROMODYNAMICS

Now we present some features in NIQCD.

A. Running coupling constant

For NIQCD, we set $N = 3$. Thus, we obtain

$$\beta_a(g) = -\frac{a^2 g^3}{16\pi^2} \left(11 - \frac{2}{3}n_f \right) \quad (36)$$

and

$$g^2(k) = \frac{g^2}{1 + \frac{a^2 g^2}{16\pi^2} \left(11 - \frac{2}{3}n_f \right) \log \left(\frac{k^2}{M^2} \right)}. \quad (37)$$

B. e^+e^- annihilation into hadrons

Also, for $N = 3$, we have [28]

$$\sigma_{\text{NLO},a}(e^+e^- \rightarrow \text{hadrons}) = 3.67\sigma_{0,a} \left(1 + \frac{\alpha_s}{\pi} + \mathcal{O}(\alpha_s^2) \right). \quad (38)$$

VI. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we have proposed a field-theoretical framework to account for non-ideal effects in quantum non-abelian gauge theories. This formulation extends the ideal case and remains valid in the non-ideal regime, being governed by the parameter a , which enhances interactions for $a > 1$ ($a < 1$) and weakens them for $a < 1$ ($a > 1$). A direct illustration of this behavior is found in the cross sections, which become larger (smaller) when $a < 1$ ($a > 1$). This interpretation is consistent with that observed in systems undergoing continuous phase transitions at low energies. We have calculated some non-ideal elementary process both at leading order (LO) and next-to-leading order (NLO), namely, $e^+e^- \rightarrow \mu^+\mu^-\gamma$ process. It cannot be computed by previously proposed non-renormalizable theories of Table IV A beyond LO, thereby restricting them to the status of effective theories. In the limit $a \rightarrow 1$, our formulation recovers all the results of the ideal case. Altogether, the findings emphasize the interplay between non-ideal features and fluctuations.

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